

NEW INCLUSIVE METHOD FOR FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7491767>

Annotation: The article is devoted to the problem of teaching students, learners, or children with disabilities in English lessons. The relevance of this problem lies in the fact that ensures the general cultural, personal and cognitive development of children.

Key words: inclusive education, innovative learning models, teaching children with disabilities, English, foreign language communication, multimedia technologies, case technology, game technologies.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена проблеме обучения студентов, учащихся или детей с ограниченными возможностями здоровья на уроках английского языка. Актуальность данной проблемы заключается в том, что она обеспечивает общекультурное, личностное и познавательное развитие детей.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное обучение, инновационные модели обучения, обучение детей с ОВЗ, английский язык, иноязычная коммуникация, мультимедийные технологии, кейс-технология, игровые технологии.

Introduction

The article is devoted to the problem of teaching students with disabilities in English lessons. The urgency of this problem lies in the fact that it is necessary to ensure the general cultural, personal and cognitive development of children with disabilities. The authors proposed methods used for productive teaching for students with disabilities, namely, multimedia and gaming technologies, case technologies, and problem-based learning. In the paper, the authors propose an example of some of the technologies used while working in general education institutions and used when working with children with disabilities in the process of inclusive education. These technologies will help teachers develop the skills and abilities of foreign language communication in children with disabilities.

In the modern world, according to statistical agencies (National Center for Health Statistics; The National Center for Education Statistic; Federal State Statistics Service, etc.), despite the development of various technologies and the field of medical services, doctors observe a significant deterioration in the health of the younger generation, this is especially true for school-age children. In this

category of citizens, there are more and more children with the status of "child with disabilities".

Researchers of this social group note that such a status seems to be a rather vague concept, since children with minor health problems and disabled children with severe cerebral palsy belong to the same category of students.

However, it should be noted that in modern pedagogical science there is a definition of this category of students: students with disabilities are children whose life activity is accompanied by any restrictions or lack of ability to carry out activities in a way that is considered normal for a person of this age.

To teach children with disabilities, the teacher needs to have the following information: understand the principles of inclusive education, have an idea about modern health-saving technologies, master the techniques of student-centered presentation of material, as well as productive learning methods.

In modern society, mastering a foreign language is becoming one of the priority tasks, which is largely due to the rapid development of telecommunications networks, various information platforms, as well as distance learning, and their general availability for all categories of the population dictates its own conditions of existence. Teaching children with disabilities a foreign language is becoming one of the main tasks of the modern educational environment.

In this case, it should be noted that having difficulties in communicating with other children due to the presence of difficulties in movement, this category of children spends a lot of time on the Internet, and to communicate with peers from other countries, you need to know foreign language. In addition, most children with disabilities of the musculoskeletal system undergo rehabilitation abroad (particularly in China), in this case, knowledge of a foreign language would be the solution to the communication problem.

Emphasis is placed on teaching listening and speaking.

This approach, according to researchers [8], is based on several methodological principles based on the psychophysiological characteristics of the studied group of students.

The principle of mobility.

Children with disabilities tend to be sedentary

way of life, therefore, when teaching a foreign language, it is recommended to adhere to the principle of mobile activities to increase motivation to study the subject, as well as to attract attention, which is often very scattered among representatives of this social group.

The principle of frequent change of activity. As already noted, children with disabilities often have distracted attention. In order to focus on learning English and performing certain learning activities, they need to change their learning activities frequently.

Creating a language environment and immersion in it. This principle involves the creation of linguocultural conditions for a more complete development of linguistic material.

Frequent listening to language structures. Children with disabilities need to combine listening to the language structure with its repetition, this will overcome the language barrier.

The principle of continuity and repeated repetition of linguistic material. Children with disabilities need to repeat the "introduced" language structures many times in order to ensure long-term storage of these structures in the memory of students. The principle of succession allows you to enter material gradually, following the principle "from simple to complex."

Disclosure of the student's creative abilities through in English. Through a foreign language (due to its diversity), a teacher can not only reveal, but also develop the student's creative abilities, which will positively affect the study of other subjects of the humanities and natural sciences.

At each lesson, which is conducted with a focus on children with disabilities, it is necessary to use various gaming technologies. Tasks presented in the form of a game help children to master the material in a relaxed atmosphere, while each task should have a clearly defined learning goal. Through the use of various didactic games, phonetic, lexical and grammatical skills, which are of paramount practical importance, since teaching children with disabilities a foreign language is carried out primarily based on listening and speaking.

Multimedia technologies play one of the leading roles in conducting modern classes in the study of a foreign language. For example, you plan to gradually develop students' understanding of English speech. Listening materials can be found on YouTube, TikTok, VKontakte platforms. There are groups on TikTok that post short videos from American and British TV series several times a day with different pronunciations of the same text. Here is practiced understanding English speech with different dialects, voices, speech rates, you can also learn many useful words and expressions.

Job example. Taking a video from YouTube, we will try to understand what it is about, play a "ball game" (the teacher pronounces the phrase in Russian, and the

student will have to translate it into English, of course, with using pre-prepared vocabulary, later complete the translation task).

Journey through virtual reality is one of the most effective and intelligible ways to inform students about certain geographical objects, creates the illusion of complete immersion in explored space.

These multimedia technologies are characterized by a high degree of interactivity, allowing you to interact with objects and examine in detail the objects of interest details. Most often, such trips allow you to walk around world capitals, visit famous museums, etc. During a foreign language lesson, such an excursion received a positive response from students.

When organizing the education of children with disabilities, it is necessary to think over the use of any gaming technologies.

The game involves all students in the learning process, regardless of their type of temperament. Game activity helps students to go through the processes of self-organization and self-affirmation, motivates them to learn a foreign language, increases their self-esteem, which allows them to better perceive and master grammatical and lexical constructions. All of the above leads to the emergence of various types of communication, contributes to the construction of the correct statement, forms an adequate speech behavior.

An important factor is also the development of creative abilities, various types of memory, thinking, increasing attention, as well as learning to communicate with both classmates and teachers. The need to introduce various Internet technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language to students with disabilities is beyond doubt, however, the material and technical equipment of places of study in this social category does not always meet the requirements.

In this regard, the use of Internet technologies becomes impossible in the process of conducting the lesson itself. As part of independent work, these technologies will make learning a foreign language more lively, fascinating and interesting, because children with certain problems with movement receive basic information from the Internet.

One of the forms of telecommunications is a podcast - a type of social service that allows you to listen, view, create and distribute audio and video broadcasts on a social network. For English learners, the podcast directory is located at the following locations:

www.podomatic.com, www.futurelearn.com,
www.BritishCouncil.com.

The use of a social podcast server in practical classes in English to develop listening skills with secondary school students diagnosed with disabilities showed quite good results.

Inclusive education is being actively introduced into modern educational system. The use of the above methods in teaching a foreign language to students with disabilities showed that this social group quickly and relatively easily masters the proposed material, they have a high motivation to learn a foreign language. However, when conducting the study, we encountered certain difficulties, in particular, teachers' lack of readiness and ability to work with students with disabilities.

Moreover, there is a problem not only professional, but also psychological readiness to work with such a group of students. With a competent solution of these problems (training courses, exchange of experience, tutor meetings, master classes, internships - remote interactive educational programs), it is possible to minimize negative manifestations of inclusion in the educational environment of students with special educational needs.

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